

An HW-In-the-Loop Approach for the Assessment of GNSS Local Channel Effects in the Railway Environment

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BIOGRAPHY

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ABSTRACT

The European Rail Traffic Management System/European Train Control System (ERTMS/ETCS) has been developed by the European Union to enhance safety and efficiency of the railway transportation. So far, the positioning and monitoring of the trains have been based mainly on trackside equipment named balises: the introduction of Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) to implement an absolute positioning system on trains could lead to a better utilization of the line with a consequent line capacity increase, along with reliability increasing and cost reducing due to the removal of expensive infrastructures. This paper describes the insertion of a state-of-the-art channel model, named Land Mobile Satellite Channel Model (LMSCM) properly adapted to represent railways scenarios, into a hardware-in-the-loop system, where the parameters generated by LMSCM are used to configure an RF GNSS signal generator. The use of the hardware generator eases the simulation of the entire GNSS constellation, while the availability of the RF signal enables the assessment of the effects of rail-domain multipath on commercial receivers. The resulting model, named Rail-Land Mobile Satellite Channel Model (Rail-LMSCM), has been enhanced with the support of different kind of scenarios a train may encounter around the rail track, as well as with the introduction of GNSS outages due to the presence of tunnels. Such enhancements make the Rail-LMSCM a more realistic average representation of the railway environment. The implemented Rail-LMSCM has been used to test in the lab the local propagation effects on the performance of a complete GNSS receiver.

INTRODUCTION

The European Rail Traffic Management System/European Train Control System (ERTMS/ETCS) has been developed by the European Union to enhance safety and efficiency of the railway transportation [1]. So far, the positioning and the monitoring of the trains have been based mainly on trackside equipment named *balises* [1]: the introduction of Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) to implement an absolute positioning system on trains could lead to a better utilization of the line with a consequent line capacity increase, along with reliability increasing and cost reducing due to the removal of expensive infrastructures [2][3]. On the other hand, the introduction of GNSS in the railway control and signaling systems poses safety and integrity issues. Although a complete GNSS integrity framework has been developed in the civil aviation field for the air traffic control, GNSS integrity studies related to train applications are less consolidated. The state of the art is however rapidly evolving thanks to the activities of some specific projects, such as STARS (Satellite Technology for Advanced Railway Signaling) [4], RHINOS (Railway High Integrity Navigation Overlay System) [5], and the Shift2rail initiative [6]. For example, the RHINOS project proposed the definition of a GNSS-based architecture of an on-board unit responsible for the train localization [7].

The most difficult factor in GNSS land applications such as the rail domain is multipath and Non-Line-Of-Sight (NLOS) propagation. GNSS signals may be reflected by obstacles surrounding the receiver; these reflected signals can interfere with the reception of the signals coming from the satellites introducing an error in the measurements performed by the receiver and, consequently, in the vehicle positioning. The amount of such multipath-induced errors should be evaluated to enable a hazard analysis for the railway application if the use of GNSS is introduced. Multipath error evaluation and mitigation has a wide and strong background in the literature and in the receiver technology [8]–[14]. However, the problem has been often approached via analytic or semi-analytic signal models [8][9], which are winning from the point of view of the simplicity of modeling and simulation, but are not suitable to realistically predict or assess the performance of a receiver exposed to a complex multipath-prone environment. The work presented in this paper aims at filling this gap, providing a means to efficiently simulate and evaluate the multipath propagation effects on GNSS receivers usable to implement next generation rail traffic management. The proposed approach is based on a hardware-in-the-loop simulation model, which combines a recognized statistical model of propagation effects with a test setup intended for complete receivers.

Several approaches can be found in literature about the assessment of multipath errors in real or realistic environments. The consolidated land mobile satellite model presented in [16] and dated 2001 uses statistical distributions to describe the various physical phenomena affecting the propagation of satellite signals in various bands, i.e. attenuation and fading due to reflections. A three-state Markov chain is employed, where, in each state, the line-of-sight (LOS) attenuation is modeled with a properly parameterized log-normal distribution, while the reflected components follow a Rayleigh distribution for the power and an exponential one for the delay. Nonetheless, the model is purely statistical and not necessarily tailored to the rail domain. Thus, many subsequent works tried to complement such a model, either with railway-specific measurement campaigns or with the introduction of wideband approaches, more suitable to characterize GNSS signal performance. For example, [17] collected measurements from GNSS-alone receivers installed on a train. The analysis of the raw measurements requires an accurate estimation of the train position that can be obtained with the data fusion of expensive sensors, and a reference receiver with a clear view of the sky. Analogously, [18][19] used a couple of cameras installed on a train to record the images of the environment along the track. The resulting videos enable to set a couple of elevation masks as a function of the vehicle position and the azimuth of the satellite: these maps enable to predict possible blockages of the LOS and the presence of reflected rays. Works [17], [18], and [19] based the analysis on real environments; alternatively, an artificial environment that mimics the real one could be used. The paper [20] introduces the Land Mobile Satellite Channel Model (LMSCM), a simulation model based on the statistics of the obstacles and the reflected rays. Given the physical characteristics of the major types of obstacles, namely house fronts, trees, poles, given the elevation and the azimuth of the satellites, as well as the velocity and attitude of the vehicle, the model randomly generates the obstacles surrounding the vehicle and the position of the reflectors, then deterministically finds the parameters of the reflected rays and the LOS blockages. The representation of signal reflections described with non-zero delays, amplitude and phase variations makes the LMSCM a ‘wideband’ model. The model was standardized by the ITU for Earth-space land mobile telecommunication systems in the L band [33]. In the two independent works [21] and [22], the authors use this LMSCM to simulate the effects of multipath on the tracking of one satellite and assess the multipath-induced errors and the effectiveness of some multipath mitigation techniques.

Some limitations affect the aforementioned examples. In [17], the use of a real environment gives punctual information about a specific track, but the results depend on the reliability of a reference system which provides the correct position of the receiver and which also could be affected by errors. The tool presented in [18] and [19] is able to predict signal blockages and non-LOS (NLOS) reception for a specific track, but it does not allow to quantify the amount of the multipath effect. The artificial environment used in [20] does not require long on-field recordings and the arrangement of a ground truth, however it cannot be directly applied to the test of commercial receivers due to the lack of the generation of the signal at Radio Frequency (RF). Moreover, it does not take into account the possible variations of the environmental characteristics that may occur along the track.

An alternative approach to enable the test of receivers in the presence of multipath is based on the use of a hardware signal generator for the generation of the RF signal. A recent example of this approach is described in [23], where authors rely on a specific interface of their signal generator to connect it with a propagation simulator, get all the propagation information (delay, Doppler and attenuation) and then generate the signal to be fed to the receiver. Similarly, [24] presents a collection of software tools and hardware devices which allow the simulation of a multipath propagation model based on a customized version of LMSCM which matches the railway environment [25]: this customization requires the availability of the source code of the basic libraries of the LMSCM.

This paper describes the insertion of the LMSCM [20] into a hardware-in-the-loop system, where the parameters generated by the LMSCM are used to configure an RF GNSS signal generator. Differently from [20], the use of the hardware generator eases the simulation of the entire GNSS constellation, while the availability of the RF signal enables the assessment of the effects of rail-domain multipath on commercial receivers. The resulting model, hereafter indicated as Rail-Land Mobile Satellite Channel Model (Rail-LMSCM), has been enhanced with the support of different kinds of scenario a train may encounter around the rail track, as well as the introduction of GNSS outages due to the presence of tunnels. This

approach is analogous to the one described in [23], but it does not require a specific model of signal generator; moreover, this simple adaptation does not require any access to the source code of the original LMSCM. Fig. 1 reports a graphical overview of the described enhancements along with the naming conventions adopted throughout the text.

The paper is organized as follows: Section I introduces LMSCM and the additions that enable to tailor it to the simulation of the railway environment; Section II describes the simplifications introduced for compatibility with the hardware signal generator and show a statistical analysis about the effects on the channel model; Sections III and IV describe the test set-up and the errors in terms of PVT and raw measurements experienced by the receiver under investigation during the elaboration of the signal affected by Rail-LMSCM. Finally, some conclusions are drawn.

Fig. 1 – From LMSCM to Rail-LMSCM

SECTION I – FROM LMSCM TO MULTI-RAY RAIL-LMSCM

The Rail-LMSCM is devoted to the simulation of local propagation effects on the GNSS signals in a railway environment, including LOS blockage, diffraction and reflections. The original LMSCM [20] allows simulating the channel affecting one satellite at a time, for a local environment with constant obstacles distributions. These are two restrictions that, respectively, *i*) limit the applicability of the simulated propagation model to a complete GNSS constellation generator, and *ii*) limit the capability of the model to realistically represent the variations of the local environment along a rail track. To overcome these limitations, some modifications have been added to the original LMSCM.

A. LMS Channel Model

The LMSCM simulates the time series of the local RF propagation effects on an L-band GNSS signal received from one satellite, namely the LOS reception and the multipath propagation; this channel model is represented as a Finite Impulse Response (FIR) filter as depicted in Fig. 2, where the outputs of the simulation model are the time series of the complex channel coefficients $\alpha_p(t)e^{j\varphi_p(t)}$ and reflection delays $\tau_p(t)$, $p = \{d1, \dots, dL, 1, \dots, N\}$.

The Channel Impulse Response (CIR) of LMSCM is written as the sum of the diffracted rays and the reflected ones

$$h(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{L(t)} \alpha_{di}(t)e^{j\varphi_{di}(t)}\delta(t - \tau_{di}(t)) + \sum_{n=1}^{N(t)} \alpha_n(t)e^{j\varphi_n(t)}\delta(t - \tau_n(t)) \quad (1)$$

where t is the current time, $L(t)$ is the number of diffracted rays, $N(t)$ is the number of the multipath rays, $\alpha_p(t)$, $\varphi_p(t)$, $\tau_p(t)$, $p = \{d1, \dots, dL, 1, \dots, N\}$ are the amplitude, phase and delay of the p -th signal component, either diffracted or reflected. When the LOS is not obscured by obstacles, in (1) the term $\alpha_{d1}(t)e^{j\varphi_{d1}(t)}\delta(t - \tau_{d1}(t))$ represents the LOS. Moreover, $L = 1$ when no diffraction occurs and $N = 0$ when no reflection is present. All the parameters in (1) are generated according to the azimuth and the elevation of the considered satellite, the velocity and the attitude of the vehicle. The number of reflections, the reflectors power, the power distribution of the echoes, and their lifespan are taken from statistics, which are tailored to either urban or suburban scenarios [20][33].

Fig. 2 - Graphical representation of LMSCM

LMSCM generates new values for all the parameters every t_{bin} seconds. In order to represent the multipath component with a sufficient resolution, the value of t_{bin} is set according to [16][22] as $t_{bin} = \frac{\lambda}{8v}$ where v is the speed of the vehicle and λ is the wavelength of the GNSS signal. For example, Table 1 reports t_{bin} for some sample values of the vehicle speed.

Table 1- Relationship between speed and time bins.

v (km/h)	t_{bin} (ms)
50	1.71
90	0.95
130	0.66

B. Rail-LMSCM: scenario transitions

The statistics of obstacles distributions reported in LMSCM refer to average environments surrounding the vehicle, representative of two possible scenarios:

- an *urban* scenario, characterized by a remarkable number of obstacles (high number of buildings);
- a *suburban* scenario, characterized by a reduced presence of obstacles (e.g. poles, trees and moderate number of buildings).

In Rail-LMSCM a third scenario has been added for completeness:

- *open sky*, characterized by a few obstacles (poles, trees and a limited number of buildings); in the case of railways application, the poles represent the power supply arches and are located at a deterministic distance from each other.

The distinguishing feature of Rail-LMSCM is that the scenario selection is not determined at the beginning of the simulation only; on the contrary, the selection may be repeated several times during the simulation, to represent the possible changes of the environmental characteristic encountered by a train. This feature has been accomplished by implementing the three scenarios defined above as the three states of a Markov chain, similarly to the approach described in [16]. The Markov chain model manages the transitions between different states by means of a *state transition probability* \mathbf{P} , where each element \mathbf{P}_{ij} is the probability of the transition from the state i to the state j . Fig. 3 depicts the resulting Markov chain, where the indexes u , s , and o indicate the states corresponding to the scenarios *urban*, *suburban*, and *open-sky* respectively.

Fig. 3- Markov chain implementing the railway scenarios

The speed of the train plays a key role in deciding whether the train has passed into a new scenario or not. Indeed, some associations between the speed of the train and the scenario are unlikely, although not impossible: a train moving slowly can be assumed as an uncommon event in an open sky scenario and, conversely, a train moving fast is a rare event in an urban one. Rail-LMSCM implements this influence of the speed on the scenario transitions using three different state transitions probability matrices, one for each speed range:

- \mathbf{P}_L for a low velocity range (e.g., up to 70 km/h);
- \mathbf{P}_M for a medium velocity range (e.g., between 70 and 120 km/h);
- \mathbf{P}_H for a high velocity range (e.g., above 120 km/h).

Therefore, when Rail-LMSCM evaluates the possible scenario transition, it uses the transition probability matrix that is compatible with the current train velocity. The current scenario determines the statistics of obstacles distributions to be used for the channel model generation. In this way the statistical characterization of the environment is open to evolve; for example, it could be modified in the future to take into account results obtained by on-going research projects devoted to the characterization of the railway environment [4][5][6]. Moreover, the number of scenarios could be further incremented to fit better the possible railway environments.

Finally, the random choice of the scenario can be disabled to allow the user of Rail-LMSCM to set a fixed scenario or a known sequence of scenarios, e.g. corresponding to a specific case of rail environment.

C. Rail-LMSCM: Rate of scenario selection

The environment in which a real train is at a given time may change after a certain travelled distance. Thus, in Rail-LMSCM, the speed of the train directly influences also the rate at which the scenario may move from one state to another: the higher the speed of the train is, the more frequently a state transition is drawn. We define as “segment” the distance between two consecutive choices (draws) of the scenario: a reasonable value for the segment length is 1 km. Accordingly, the rate of scenario selection is $\frac{1}{t_{segment}} = \frac{v}{1 \text{ km}}$ where v is the velocity of the train. Thus, Rail-LMSCM can change the statistics of the obstacles and reflections every $t_{segment}$ seconds, when a new segment selection is performed, with probabilities described in one of the transition matrices $\mathbf{P}_L, \mathbf{P}_M, \mathbf{P}_H$.

D. Rail-LMSCM: Tunnels

Tunnels are often present along rail tracks; however, they are completely different from the scenarios described so far, because they cause a complete outage of all the GNSS signals, implying the absence of any LOS, diffracted and reflected signal. An example of statistics of tunnel length and inter-tunnels distance for the railway domain can be found in [34]. The possible presence of tunnels is implemented in Rail-LMSCM through the insertion of a *random flag* that overwrites the current scenario, disabling all the GNSS signals: the flag is drawn as an instance of a statistical distribution that considers both the tunnel length and the inter-tunnel distance.

E. Rail-LMSCM multi-ray: assessment of tracking errors

In order to assess the effectiveness of the features added to get Rail-LMSCM multi-ray from LMSCM, the tracking errors caused by the channel model have been evaluated for different scenarios and satellite elevations, as reported in Table 2.

Table 2 – Simulated scenarios and satellite elevation values

Scenario	User velocity [km/h]	Satellite elevation angles [deg]
Urban	50	20, 40, 60, 80
Suburban	90	20, 40, 60, 80
Open-sky	130	20, 40, 60, 80

For each combination of scenario and satellite elevation in Table 2, the CIR of Rail-LMSCM multi-ray has been generated with the parameters listed in Table 3.

Fig. 4 reports a block scheme describing the performed simulation. A stream of GPS L1 C/A raw samples at base band (BB) are generated through N-FUELS [21]: this tool enables the generation of a stream of sample for a GNSS signal allowing the user to configure all the signal characteristics, amongst them, the initial code delay and the Doppler shift. The CIR of the multi-ray is generated for the current scenario and satellite elevation. Then, a Finite Impulse Response (FIR) filter is used to apply the CIR to the sample stream: the filtered samples are elaborated by a simple tracking routine made of a PLL and a DLL, without any countermeasure against the multipath effects. The estimated code delays are then compared with correct values, which are known since both initial code delay and the Doppler have been configured through N-FUELS: this allows the error analysis reported in Table 4.

Table 3 – Other parameters used for multi-ray channel model generation

Parameter	Used value
User trajectory	Straight S-N
User velocity	Constant depending on the simulated scenario
Satellite azimuth	90° (cross-track)
Satellite elevation	One elevation value constant during the simulation
Scenario	One scenario fixed for the complete duration of each simulation
Duration	3 minutes

Fig. 4- Tracking error assessment for multi-ray

The current scenario affects the obtained pseudorange errors as reported in Table 4: both mean and standard deviation increases when passing from the open-sky scenario to the urban one. Also the effects of the satellite elevation are visible, above all in the urban and suburban scenarios, whereas, in open-sky, only the lowest elevation value shows a clear impact on the pseudorange error statistics.

Table 4 - Assessment of tracking error for multi-ray

Scenario	Satellite elevation [deg]	Mean tracking error [m]	Tracking error std [m]
Urban	20	26.63	19.77
	40	3.5	6.04
	60	1.42	2.28
	80	0.78	0.62
Suburban	20	9.16	8.95
	40	2.70	4.15
	60	0.76	0.60
	80	0.77	0.59
Open-sky	20	3.18	5.68
	40	0.89	0.71
	60	0.74	0.58
	80	0.71	0.56

In order to separate the effects due to the LOS fading from the effects from the reflections, the presented simulation has been repeated after excluding the fading of the LOS. Referring to (1), this has been obtained by setting $L(t) = 1$, $\alpha_{d1}(t) = 1$, and

$\varphi_{d1}(t) = 0$ for all the duration of the simulation. Other parameters are not changed w.r.t. the values reported in Table 2 and Table 3. Table 5 reports the statistics of the obtained tracking errors: the comparison with Table 4 leads to the conclusion that the pseudorange errors are strongly reduced when the fading of the LOS is omitted: this means that, according to the LMSCM, the major effect of tracking error is caused by the fading process on the LOS signal, while delayed multipath rays, in any of the considered scenarios, have only marginal effects.

Table 5 - Assessment of tracking error for multi-ray, reflections only

Scenario	Satellite Elevation [deg]	Mean tracking error [m]	Tracking error std [m]
Urban	20	1.09	0.9
	40	1.0	0.86
	60	0.95	0.8
	80	0.72	0.57
Suburban	20	1.19	0.97
	40	0.89	0.70
	60	0.75	0.6
	80	0.77	0.6
Open-sky	20	0.91	0.74
	40	0.85	0.69
	60	0.73	0.55
	80	0.71	0.56

SECTION II – HARDWARE IN THE LOOP APPROACH

Section I has shown how the Rail-LMSCM multi-ray has been got from LMSCM through the addition of different scenarios and tunnels. The enhancements discussed so far make the Rail-LMSCM multi-ray a more realistic average representation of the railway environment. The main limitations of such channel model are the support of just one satellite and the absence of the generation of the signal at RF, which make impossible the assessment of the multipath effects on the PVT results.

In order to obtain the generation of the signal at RF, a hardware-in-the-loop approach has been used, analogous to the one described in [23], where authors interface a propagation simulator with the GNSS simulator software by means of a package of remote-control facilities: the propagation simulator is able to calculate the propagation information of the reflected signals starting from a 3D urban model.

In this work, the generation of the multipath impaired GNSS RF signal has been obtained through the use of a signal generator that, differently from the model employed in [23], does not possess specific features for the integration of a propagation simulator. The employed simulator, namely an IFEN NavX–NCS Professional [36], supports two kinds of multipath influences: reflections from the ground and multipath with fixed offset: this means that the standard support of the multipath of the signal generator is not enough to cope with the Rail-LMSCM multi-ray described in this paper. In order to overcome this limitation, other available features of the generator have been considered:

- the orbits and the clock errors of the simulated satellites can be configured through RINEX or almanac files;
- the broadcast navigation message for the simulated satellites can be configured through RINEX or almanac files;
 - the content of the navigation message can differ from the simulated orbits and clock errors;
- the signal power level for each generated signal can be configured through a text file;
- the spreading codes can be specified by the user.

These listed features have been used to configure the signal generator to apply the CIR reported in (1) to the generated signal.

A. Rail-LMSCM for RF generation: reducing the number of reflections

The reproduction of Rail-LMSCM multi-ray in a hardware RF signal generator, as introduced earlier in this section, requires the availability of one hardware resource (the so-called ‘hardware channel’) for each signal reflection, plus the LOS component, i.e. $L(t) + N(t)$ hardware channels in the notation introduced in (1). Consequently, the number of hardware channels practically available in the hardware signal generator limits the number of rays that is possible to generate. For this reason, the number of reflected and diffracted signals generated by Rail-LMSCM multi-ray must be drastically reduced to meet the number of available hardware channels. For example, the employed signal generator supports 24 hardware channels, which means the possibility to generate up to

- 24 satellites in a no-multipath condition;
- 12 satellites when $L + N = 2$, i.e. a channel model with up to two rays;
- 8 satellites when $L + N = 3$, i.e. a channel model with up to three rays.

Fig. 5 - CIR for a two-ray Rail-LMSCM

Several methods able to reduce the number of rays in a multipath channel model while maintaining the main characteristics of the complete model are reported in literature. Readers can find a list of approaches and a performance comparison in [26]: this analysis includes models based on the Tapped Delay Line approach [27][28], the channel clustering techniques [29][30], the optimization of parameters to preserve the autocorrelation function [31] or the statistical distribution of the reduced channel parameters [32].

Considering the marginal effect of the multipath rays observed in Table 5, hereafter we discuss the possibility of reducing the number of reflections to one, thus obtaining a *two-ray model*, composed of one LOS and one reflected signal, as depicted in Fig. 5: The CIR of the resulting two-ray channel model is

$$h(t) = \alpha_d(t)e^{j\varphi_d(t)}\delta(t - \tau_d(t)) + \alpha_1(t)e^{j\varphi_1(t)}\delta(t - \tau_1(t)) \quad (2)$$

The employed simplification is an application of the tap delay line approach presented in [26] where the target number of reflected rays is set to one. In the Rail-LMSCM two-ray, at each time instant the parameters are chosen in this way:

- the time delay τ_1 is equal to the delay of the reflected ray with the strongest power in (1);
- the complex coefficient $\alpha_1 e^{j\varphi_1}$ is the sum of the complex coefficients of all the reflected rays currently present in the multi-ray model;
- the delay τ_d is equal to the delay of the LOS;
- the complex coefficient $\alpha_d e^{j\varphi_d}$ is the complex sum of the coefficients in the first summation of (1).

Furthermore, in order to reduce the ‘representation loss’ between the multi-ray and the two-ray-model, a *three-ray model* has been implemented, which is equivalent to the two-ray model with the addition of a second reflected ray:

$$h(t) = \alpha_d(t)e^{j\varphi_d(t)}\delta(t - \tau_d(t)) + \alpha_1(t)e^{j\varphi_1(t)}\delta(t - \tau_1(t)) + \alpha_2(t)e^{j\varphi_2(t)}\delta(t - \tau_2(t)) \quad (3)$$

where the first reflected ray has the same values used in the two-ray model, whereas for the second one we used a criterion based on the minimization of *Root Mean Square (RMS) delay spread* [39]. The RMS delay spread is defined as:

$$\sigma_\tau = \sqrt{\overline{\tau^2} - (\bar{\tau})^2} \quad (4)$$

where

$$\bar{\tau} = \frac{\sum_n \alpha_n^2 \tau_n}{\sum_n \alpha_n^2} \quad (5)$$

$$\overline{\tau^2} = \frac{\sum_n \alpha_n^2 \tau_n^2}{\sum_n \alpha_n^2} \quad (6)$$

The second reflected ray is selected as the one that minimizes the difference between the multi-ray channel model and the three-ray one in terms of RMS delay spread.

B. Statistical analysis for the reduced Rail-LMSCM

To verify the amount of inevitable representation loss caused by the reduction of the number of rays in Rail-LMSCM two-ray and three-ray, some statistical metrics have been analyzed, namely the power delay profile, the RMS delay spread, the power spectral density and the coherence bandwidth. During this analysis, the channel model for a single satellite has been considered with different configurations as reported in Table 2 and Table 3.

1. Power Delay Profile

The power-delay profile (PDP) is a function that describes the average power of the reflections, relative to the LOS power, as a function of their delay [15]. A comparison, in terms of time-averaged PDP, between the multi-ray, two-ray and three-ray models is plotted in Fig. 6 for the three scenarios urban, suburban and open-sky. For the sake of brevity, the results for one value of satellite elevation are reported, namely the 40° elevation, since for other values the results are analogous. Notice that the maximum delay for all the reflections was set to 0.6 μs . Results reported in Fig. 6 show the difference introduced by the simplification of the multi-ray channel model and confirm the intuitive deduction for which the three-ray simplification resembles the complete multi-ray channel model better than the two-ray simplification.

Fig. 6 - PDP for multi-ray, two-ray and three-ray in different scenarios

2. RMS delay spread

The RMS delay spread, defined by (4), (5), and (6), has been evaluated for all the configurations in Table 2 and Table 3 and is reported in Table 6. We notice that the current scenario clearly impacts only the case of urban environment, whereas the differences between suburban and open-sky are not so evident. Finally, in agreement with the previous analysis, the three-ray simplification approximates the multi-ray better than the two-ray simplification.

Table 6 - RMS delay spread for two-ray, three-ray, and multi-ray in different scenarios and with different satellite elevations

Scenario	Elevation [deg]	RMS delay-spread [ns]		
		two-ray	three-ray	multi-ray
Urban	20	107	124	130
Urban	40	29.4	45.4	71.5
Urban	60	22.5	38.7	63.6
Urban	80	15.7	27.1	43.0
Suburban	20	21.2	43.5	75.5
Suburban	40	19.2	36.1	61.1
Suburban	60	16.7	28.0	48.5
Suburban	80	17.4	27.5	44.9
Open-sky	20	32.7	57.0	87.4
Open-sky	40	34.9	59.4	87.8
Open-sky	60	20.6	32.7	52.7
Open-sky	80	16.5	26.8	44.3

3. Power Spectral Density and Coherence Bandwidth

In this section, the frequency analysis of the CIR is reported. The magnitude of the frequency response of multi-ray, three-ray and two-ray is shown in Fig. 7 for the three scenarios. As before, the satellite elevation used during the tests is 40°, when other values lead to analogous results. The results reported by Fig. 7 confirm the differences found between the multi-ray channel model and the simplified ones reported in the previous sections. To get a quantitative assessment of the difference, the coherence bandwidth has been analyzed. The coherence bandwidth is used to characterize the channel in the frequency domain: it is a statistical measure of the frequency range where the channel can be considered “flat” [39]. Commonly, the coherence bandwidth is defined as the bandwidth over which the value of the CIR autocorrelation (delay spread) is at least 0.5 [39]. Table 7 reports the coherence bandwidth for different scenarios and different satellite elevation values: from these values we can see that the two-ray channel model implies an increment of the coherence bandwidth, whereas the three-ray reduces it.

Fig. 7- Average magnitude of the frequency response of multi-ray, two-ray, and three-ray models in different scenarios

Table 7 - Coherence bandwidth for different scenarios and satellite elevations

Scenario	Elevation [deg]	Coherence bandwidth [MHz]		
		two-ray	three-ray	multi-ray
Urban	20	2.18	1.87	2.17
Urban	40	2.52	1.74	2.03
Urban	60	2.71	1.84	2.07
Urban	80	2.60	2.24	2.42
Suburban	20	2.05	1.83	2.10
Suburban	40	1.92	1.81	2.05
Suburban	60	2.27	1.95	2.06
Suburban	80	1.78	1.90	2.03
Open-sky	20	2.05	1.79	2.08
Open-sky	40	1.90	1.77	2.12
Open-sky	60	1.82	1.88	2.05
Open-sky	80	2.31	2.06	2.21

4. Time coherence

The time coherence T_c is the measure of the time during which the channel can be assumed as non-variant. To test how long the channel input response does not vary over time, the duration of each reflected ray has been evaluated for different scenarios and a satellite elevation equal to 40°. Fig. 8 shows a zoomed view around the 90th percentile of the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of the reflected rays' duration. Table 8 reports the 95th percentile of the coherence time for all the tests and the channel models under investigation. Fig. 8 and Table 8 show that the reflected rays have a duration which is inversely proportional to the speed of the vehicle; as expected lower velocity (i.e. urban scenario) implies longer duration. The two-ray and three-ray channel models show a shorter coherence time w.r.t. the multi-ray one, which is implicitly due to the constrained reduction of the number of reflections. For this metric, the two-ray channel model approximates better the multi-ray than the three-ray.

Fig. 8- Cumulative distribution function of the duration of the reflected rays for different scenarios

Table 8 – Coherence time (95th percentile) for different scenarios and satellite elevations

Scenario	Elevation [deg]	Coherence time, 95 th percentile [ms]		
		two-ray	three-ray	multi-ray
Urban	20	54.8	48.0	101.2
Urban	40	82.3	63.5	138.9
Urban	60	78.9	61.7	128.6
Urban	80	75.4	60.0	120.1
Suburban	20	52.4	36.2	83.8
Suburban	40	46.7	34.3	72.4
Suburban	60	43.8	36.2	68.6
Suburban	80	39.0	32.4	63.8
Open-sky	20	34.3	25.0	56.0
Open-sky	40	35.6	25.7	55.4
Open-sky	60	31.6	25.0	50.8
Open-sky	80	29.7	23.7	46.1

5. Pseudorange errors

Another metric to assess the behaviour of the simplifications of the channel model is the evaluation of the induced tracking error in a reference receiver as described in Section I.E. The multi-ray, two-ray and three-ray channel models have been used to generate in software the base-band samples of the GNSS signals with the configurations reported in Table 2 and Table 3. The duration of each simulation is reduced to 1 minute to cope with the increased number of simulations. The statistics of the errors induced on the tracking stage are reported in Table 9.

Table 9 - Tracking errors statistics for different channels models in case of different scenarios and satellite elevations

Scenario	Satellite elevation [deg]	Tracking error, mean [m]			Tracking error, standard deviation [m]		
		multi-ray	two-ray	three-ray	multi-ray	two-ray	three-ray
Urban	20	33.10	20.82	28.47	17.91	15.34	16.74
	40	1.47	0.87	1.07	1.91	1.03	1.38
	60	1.19	0.72	0.87	1.33	0.64	0.87
	80	0.78	0.63	0.67	0.62	0.47	0.51
Suburban	20	9.67	3.62	5.19	9.64	4.10	5.52
	40	3.51	1.70	2.18	5.02	2.42	3.10
	60	0.67	0.62	0.62	0.51	0.46	0.48
	80	0.81	0.63	0.65	0.64	0.49	0.50
Open-sky	20	4.00	1.88	2.49	6.26	2.91	3.84
	40	0.77	0.61	0.64	0.60	0.45	0.47
	60	0.73	0.61	0.65	0.56	0.47	0.47
	80	0.76	0.59	0.64	0.59	0.44	0.47

Fig. 9 - Cumulative distribution of the tracking errors for a satellite at medium elevation

We can conclude that the analysed simplifications lead to a decrease in the standard deviation and the mean value of the tracking error. Moreover, the three-ray model shows less impact on the estimated tracking error than the two-ray simplification. Finally, it is possible to analyse the distribution of the tracking errors. Fig. 9 reports an example of this analysis for the satellite at 40° elevation at different scenarios: the three-ray simplification slightly increases the similarity with multi-ray w.r.t. the two-ray simplification. Results for other satellite elevation values are analogous.

C. Comments

Section II.B reported the statistical analysis of the channel model reduction strategies presented in II.A: these results assess the differences between the multi-ray and the two-ray/three-ray channel models. The reduced channel models are a gross simplification of the original multi-ray channel model, but they are needed to grant the compatibility with the employed hardware generator. It must be noticed that this limitation does not spoil the validity of the hardware-in-the-loop approach presented here, which can be improved by increasing the number of available hardware channels.

SECTION III – TEST SET-UP

The Rail-LMSCM can be used to test the local propagation effects on the tracking stage of a GNSS receiver, provided that the analysis is able to separate such effects from other impairments. Fig. 10 depicts the set-up used for the tests which includes a 24-channels hardware signal generator and a commercial GNSS receiver (namely an IFEN NavX–NCS Professional and a uBlox 6 GPS receiver). The generation of the RF signal is performed twice:

- “Run0”, the signal generator is configured to generate a ‘clean’ signal ensemble along a trajectory, without local propagation effects. The corresponding log will be used for reference.
- “Run1”, the signal generator is configured to add the propagation effects to the simulated signal previously modelled with the two-ray Rail-LMSCM.

Fig. 10 - The used test set-up

This set-up is different from the one depicted in Fig. 4, because the assessment of tracking errors described in Section II requires the generation of the signal for a single satellite, whereas the test of the receiver needs the simulation of the complete constellation. In Fig. 10, all the information needed to generate the Rail-LMSCM and the RF signal are extracted from a train trajectory and a RINEX navigation file. A trajectory is described by three elements, each one represented by a time series: the time, the position and the velocity of the train. Two different kinds of trajectories could be considered

- artificial trajectories, generated ad hoc in order to have full control of all the simulation conditions;
- realistic trajectories, which mimic the real movement of a train along a real portion of railway and can be extracted from the log of a positioning system mounted on a train.

Each reference trajectory, once associated to the simulation of the propagation channel, gives rise to a reference track.

The comparison between the measurements in *Run0* and *Run1* allows to easily discard the satellite clock error and the tropospheric and ionospheric errors, whereas the receiver clock bias can be removed by using the value estimated by the PVT computation: in this way the local propagation effects are isolated. In the following paragraphs, e_{ρ}^s and e_{ϕ}^s will indicate the errors for the code based pseudorange and the carrier phase measurements for the satellite s .

SECTION IV – RAIL-LMSCM: EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The test set-up described in Section III has been used to check the local propagation effects simulated by the Rail-LMSCM in different scenarios.

In order to get this goal, three reference tracks have been defined and used to generate the channel model; Table 10 reports the main characteristics of these tracks, which have been named *Tr01*, *Tr02*, and *Tr03*.

Table 10 – List of reference tracks

Track ID	Tr01	Tr02	Tr03
Kind of trajectory	Artificial	Artificial	Artificial
Description	Straight trajectory from South to North at a constant speed. Medium latitude.		
Vehicle Speed	50 km/h	90 km/h	130 km/h
Scenario	Urban	Suburban	Open-sky
Duration	3'	3'	3'
Distance over ground	2.5 km	4.5 km	6.5 km
Tunnel	None	None	None
Antenna radiation pattern	Omni directional	Omni directional	Omni directional
Employed channel model	Two-ray	Two-ray	Two-ray

All the reference tracks reported in Table 10 are artificial because this kind of trajectory is enough to simulate the effects of different scenarios. It must be noticed that the proposed implementation of the Rail-LMSCM and the described set-up support realistic trajectories without the need for any adaptation.

For each test and each simulated satellite, a complete statistical analysis of the raw measurements saved by the target GNSS receiver has been performed. The following tables report the results of this analysis for each track.

Table 11 - Raw measurement analysis for Tr01

PRN (GPS)	2	12	14	21	25	26	29	31	32
Availability (%)	97.8	99.4	99.4	100	100	93.4	100	100	96.1
Mean e_{ρ}^s [m]	2.1	4.7	7.0	-1.2	-2.2	12.3	-2.1	-1.7	7.3
e_{ρ}^s std [m]	4.3	6.0	7.7	1.5	1.5	9.7	1.4	1.7	8.9
Mean e_{ϕ}^s [m]	0.05	-2.49	-0.06	0.15	0.19	-0.2	0.11	0.14	-0.43
e_{ϕ}^s std [m]	1.42	28.96	1.97	0.31	0.33	2.82	0.31	0.34	2.29

Table 12 - Raw measurements analysis for Tr02

PRN (GPS)	2	12	14	21	25	26	29	31	32
Availability (%)	100	98.3	97.8	100	100	93.4	100	100	96.1
Mean e_{ρ}^s [m]	0.5	1.6	2.0	-2.6	-2.5	5.0	-2.7	-2.8	6.1
e_{ρ}^s std [m]	3.7	4.6	5.0	1.2	1.0	8.8	1.0	1.0	7.7
Mean e_{ϕ}^s [m]	-0.1	-0.12	0.16	0.09	0.1	0.86	0.01	0.09	-0.07
e_{ϕ}^s std [m]	1.29	1.08	1.39	0.27	0.28	10.86	0.27	0.27	1.69

Table 13 - Raw measurement analysis for Tr03

PRN (GPS)	2	12	14	21	25	26	29	31	32
Availability (%)	100	100	100	100	100	98.9	100	100	99.4
Mean e_{ρ}^s [m]	-0.7	-0.4	-0.1	-0.9	-0.9	0.4	-1.0	-0.9	0.3
e_{ρ}^s std [m]	0.8	0.8	1.0	0.8	0.8	2.3	0.8	0.9	1.9
Mean e_{ϕ}^s [m]	0.01	0.04	0.03	0.01	-0.01	-0.04	0.01	0.01	-0.01
e_{ϕ}^s std [m]	0.18	0.19	0.22	0.17	0.19	0.53	0.19	0.17	0.29

Each table reports the result for one scenario: if we compare the digits for the same satellites in different scenarios we can see that, generally, the urban scenario (Tr01, Table 11) exhibits the highest errors and the lowest availability (i.e. percentage of PVT computation where the measurements are available w.r.t. the total number of PVT computations). On the contrary, the

open-sky scenario (Tr03, Table 13) has the lowest errors and the highest availability. This confirms that the Rail-LMSCM implementation is able to mimic different scenarios.

In the same table, different satellites show very different values for the estimated measurements errors. E.g., in Table 11, the average code pseudorange error goes from about 1 meter for GPS 21 to about 12 meters for GPS 26. These differences can be explained by considering the elevation and the azimuth of the different satellites, which are reported in Table 14. Measurements for satellites with high elevation show reduced errors, whereas satellites with low elevation have errors which depend also on the azimuth. Satellites with low elevation but appearing along the direction of the track (N-S) have reduced errors, similar to those of satellites at high elevation (e.g., GPS 21). Also, this result confirms that the Rail-LMSCM implementation is able to recreate the realistic conditions, where the signals from satellites with low elevation are seemingly the most impaired by the multipath effects.

Table 14 - Elevation and azimuth for the simulated satellites

PRN (GPS)	2	12	14	21	25	26	29	31	32
Elevation [deg]	29	27	22	13	64	12	87	49	14
Azimuth [deg]	51	93	253	184	78	289	262	299	235

Finally, the position error has been evaluated; Table 15 reports the position errors for each trajectory and both the runs. *Run1* for different scenarios led to different position error statistics, where generally the urban scenario shows the largest errors and the open-sky scenario the smallest ones. The results from the *Run0* of each track have been reported, too: in this case, the positioning error is almost unaffected by the change of scenario which is a direct consequence from the fact that in *Run0* the channel model is not applied to the signal generator configuration. It must be noticed that errors in the broadcast ephemerides, satellite clock parameters, and atmospheric models parameters are not simulated.

Table 15 - Position error

Track/Run	Tr01/Run0	Tr01/Run1	Tr02/Run0	Tr02/Run1	Tr03/Run0	Tr03/Run1
2D error mean (m)	0.07	1.4	0.09	0.8	0.12	0.24
2D error std (m)	0.04	1.14	0.04	0.69	0.03	0.16
3D error mean (m)	0.13	1.99	0.15	2.14	0.16	0.87
3D error std (m)	0.04	1.14	0.04	0.69	0.03	0.16

CONCLUSION

In this paper, a standard LMSCM has been completed with the addition of different scenarios and then adapted to the use with an RF GNSS signal generator: the adaption has been described and the effects of the conversion from a multi-ray channel model to a two-ray/three-ray one have been presented and analyzed. The effects of the resulting Rail-LMSCM on the measurements and the positions evaluated by a commercial receiver confirm the suitability of the proposed approach in the simulation of the local propagation effects. The use of the RF GNSS signal generator grants the possibility to quickly repeat the same simulation on different receivers, allowing to state the effectiveness of the employed multipath mitigation techniques, whereas the support of different scenarios allows the test of the multipath effects also in presence of realistic trajectories which mimic the real movement of a train along a real portion of railway and can be extracted from the log of a positioning system mounted on a train. Finally, the presented approach based on scenarios and use of hardware generator is compatible with evolved versions of the original LMSCM and sophisticated channel model response reduction algorithms.

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